

BASIC CONCEPTS AND STYLES OF LEADERSHI

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Abstract. This article highlights the activities of a leader: basic concepts, styles and methods of leadership; and what personal qualities a leader should possess. It states that a leader's culture and skill are considered high indicators of the art of management.

Keywords: leader, activity, skill, approach, style, method, team, goal, action, interest, openness, transparency, freedom, creativity, quality, non-standard, situation, image, curiosity, talent. In this article, the activities of a leader are highlighted: basic concepts, methods, and techniques of leadership; what personal qualities a leader should possess.

Today, a common problem in leadership activities is the issue of the organic and logical interconnection between a leader's culture, spirituality, and managerial skills. Management skills, in turn, are connected with the culture and spiritual-intellectual world of today's leader, through which their image (positive or negative) is formed in the eyes of employees.

Leadership is the process of managing, guiding, organizing, and inspiring a group of people towards a common goal. Leadership styles are management methods that depend on how a leader interacts with their team, how they manage them, and what decisions they make. [1.]

The authoritarian (bordering on coercive) leadership style is a leadership approach based on the leader making all decisions independently, giving strict orders to employees, and enforcing control and discipline without question. Leadership styles are management methods that depend on how a leader interacts with their team, how they manage them, and what decisions they make.

The main characteristics of an authoritarian leader include the following: first, decisions are made and implemented solely by the leader; second, employees' opinions are not considered or sought; third, employees are under strict supervision with strong control at every stage of work; fourth, there is a command-based approach where tasks are given as orders; fifth, communication is one-sided with only the leader speaking while others obey.

The main characteristics of an authoritarian manager include the following: firstly, decisions are made and implemented only by the manager themselves, secondly, the opinion of employees is not taken into account or asked for, thirdly, the employee is under strict control, and control in each work process is strong, fourthly, command, that is, tasks are given as orders, fifthly, communication is one-sided in which only the manager speaks, others obey.

The advantages of an authoritarian leader are that they are effective in emergency situations, the work process is strictly controlled, and the leader is responsible for all decisions. The disadvantages of managing an authoritarian leader in this regard are that employees become mentally exhausted, creativity fades, motivation decreases, and circular stress accelerates. That is, the feeling of fear and pressure on employees increases

significantly, they feel no incentive to take initiative, the employee feels worthless, and personnel change frequently. The authoritarian method can be effective in military systems, in emergency situations, in situations requiring a high level of danger and responsibility, and for a short period of time.

Democratic leadership is a management style based on the leader's collaboration with the team, consultation, decision-making, and involvement of all participants in the process. In this style, the leader becomes a leader who not only commands but also listens, understands, and inspires.

The main characteristics of democratic leadership include: firstly, cooperation and consultation; all decisions are discussed with the team; secondly, receiving opinions and suggestions; the manager listens to and evaluates employees' opinions; thirdly, an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect is formed in the team; fourthly, responsibility distribution; objective distribution of tasks and instructions; fifthly, employees encouraged by creativity are encouraged to express their opinions freely. [2.]

The advantages of democratic leadership are that employees feel valued, generate new ideas, strengthen solidarity through collective decisions, and reduce the likelihood of employees leaving their workplace. Democratic leadership can also have shortcomings. These can take time to consult with many people, sometimes make it difficult to make firm decisions, and there may be disagreements in some decisions.

The effectiveness of applying the democratic style is important in organizations that carry out creative or intellectual activities (education, IT, research, marketing, etc.), when employees are independent-minded and responsible, and when it is necessary to introduce innovations and make collective decisions. For example, imagine that a school principal is planning to introduce a new curriculum. He holds a meeting with teachers and class teachers, listens to the opinions of each of them, and, based on them, formulates the final program. This is democracy!

A liberal (free) leadership style is a management style that gives employees maximum freedom, independence, and initiative. In this style, the leader is not the central figure, but rather entrusts management to the team and reduces control.

The main characteristics of liberal leadership include: firstly, the leader plays a passive role, providing only the necessary resources; secondly, employees work independently and make decisions by them; thirdly, the leader's control is minimal and interference in the work process is minimal; fourthly, a creative and free environment creates broad opportunities for initiative and innovation; fifthly, the tendency for self-management and self-organization of the team remains strong.

The advantages of the liberal leadership style are that employees freely implement their ideas, the team chooses its own direction, everyone is responsible for their work, and the team responds to urgent situations with free decisions.

The disadvantages of the liberal leadership style are as follows: firstly, lack of control can lead to delays and the loss of clear goals; secondly, if a problem arises due to a lack of leadership, it becomes unclear who will be held accountable; thirdly, instability in the work process can lead to some employees being active and others passive; and fourthly, it can be difficult to assess work quality, resulting in a lack of criteria. [3.]

The effectiveness of the liberal leadership style is expedient if it is used in creative organizations (design studio, IT startup, research laboratories), in teams where highly

qualified, knowledgeable specialists work, in systems where independent and self-organizing groups operate. Example (from real life): In one advertising agency, executives rarely interfere with employees. Every designer, marketer, or editor independently plans, performs, and is responsible for the results of their work. The manager only defines the overall strategy and provides resources. This is an example of a liberal style.

The liberal leadership style is based on trust, independence, and creativity. It stimulates the personal initiative of employees, but can also lead to a weakening of management. To apply this style as a manager, employees must be sufficiently responsible and experienced, and tasks must be clearly defined in advance. [4.]

The spirituality of a leader, firstly, is a hidden force influencing ordinary employees; secondly, it directs management personnel to work actively towards a specific goal; thirdly, it is a factor in solving socio-economic and political problems; fourthly, it should be a mechanism that mobilizes the team, organization, enterprise, institution for the successful fulfillment of tasks; fifthly, it should have the characteristics of educating the team, especially schoolchildren, students, and youth, as well as implementing a number of other tasks.

In the management process, a leader operates within a specific team. The effectiveness of the leader's work is created on the basis of joint actions aimed at achieving common goals. The interests of the leader and the team do not always coincide.

One of the important tasks of the leader and the team as a whole is the creation of favorable conditions for harmonizing the interests of the team and the individual. It is necessary to create a rational system of internal rules and regulations, norms that fully correspond to the interests of each individual and the collective as a single, unified social organism. The success of the team's activities largely depends on what conditions are created for the team's growth and development, and how well each member of the team can meet their needs.

However, the employee's personality needs to manifest itself, prove its uniqueness, originality, and stand out from other people in the team with special characteristics. An individual, understanding the requirements they place on each member of the collective and adhering to the requirements of society's spirituality and morality, may occasionally be in a mood or attitude contrary to general principles. [5.]

In conclusion, the managerial relations of a modern leader in internal affairs bodies consist of directing the team towards strategic goals, establishing effective cooperation based on open dialogue, developing personnel, and increasing the effectiveness of the organization through the use of modern management tools. Such leaders play an important role in improving professionalism in the organization and strengthening public trust.

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